

Constitutional-legal ways of protection of rights and freedoms of minors in system of juvenile justice

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Abstract. Protection of life and health of youth and formation in this regard of state policy on protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of younger generation as independent activity of state bodies and society in general is one of the priority tasks designated in Strategy "Kazakhstan-2030". The social essence of state legal policy (juvenile policy) on realization of protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of minors, and in this aspect the value of right is that it carries out regulating impact on the public relations.

Keywords: rights and freedoms of minors, juvenile justice, state policy, realization of right.

Protection of life and health of youth and formation in this regard of state policy on protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of younger generation as independent activity of state bodies and society in general is one of the priority tasks designated in Strategy "Kazakhstan-2030" [1, page 32].

The social essence of state legal policy (juvenile policy) on realization of protection of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of minors, and in this aspect the value of right is that it carries out regulating impact on the public relations, forming defined "measured environment" (B. A. Kistyakovsky) of [2] interactions of subjects in a certain space of time. In this context, Russian pre-revolutionary lawyer S. A. Muromtsev absolutely fairly noted in due time that the right "is only means to achievement of some cultural purposes" therefore its functioning "has to be estimated from the point of view of the purposes" [3, page 51]. It is obvious that the right as however, state juvenile policy conforms to the certain functional requirements consisting in providing rather steady and stable existence of social system, its integrity and unity, protection of the national and cultural standardized activity

providing succession and reproduction basic (valuable and motivational, spiritual and moral, etc.) integration bases of concrete society in questions of full development of institute of rights and freedoms of child.

The mechanism of realization of right – component element of mechanism of legal regulation, research of which is one of the main problems of modern legal science [4, page 14]. In this regard the functional nature and social usefulness of right is expressed in its ability of establishment and protection socially recognized and generally acceptable reference points, ideals, programs of human behavior providing balance of vital interests in system "personality – society – state". This advantage can be also expressed in organization of rather strong and stable social-legal and ethnopolitical order, adjustment historically and culturally caused relations of justice in information, production, exchange and distributive relations, emergence of objective criteria in an assessment of acts of social behavior, etc. [5, page 6].

Thus, without process of embodiment of right in direct life it is impossible to understand neither its essence, nor its social appointment, especially in questions of realization of state juvenile policy.

Famous theorist of law L.S. Yavich wrote that "implementation of right – a way of life, existence, action, performance of the main social function of it. The right is nothing if its provisions don't find realization in activity of people and their organization, in public relations. It is impossible to understand the right if to distract from the mechanism of its realization in life of society" [6, page 200-201].

Proceeding from the maintenance of aforesaid, to understand legal essence and legal value of institute of realization and protection of rights and freedoms of minors, first of all, it is necessary to analyze semantic concept of legal categories "realization of right" and "protection of right".

The word "realization" literally comes from Latin "realis" – "material" and literally means objectification. Presently "realization" is defined as implementation of something, carrying out in life of any plan, project, program, intention, etc.

The term "realization of right" is similar on sense. The right as something non-material as a certain opportunity is realized, carried out in actions, in active behavior of people, in use of material and cultural wealth, benefits [7, page 179]. From here

becomes clear that though adoption of laws and other normative legal acts extremely important, crucial importance has implementation in our life, in practice of obligatory requirements containing in them.

Norms formulated in laws and other normative legal acts only then become live when they are embodied actually, and realized in conscious and strong-willed acts (actions) of people [8, page 605].

What does realization of right represent, and in what forms it is shown? There is a huge massif of literature devoted to consideration of this question. Realization of right, as well as its forms, is understood far unequally. In one cases speak about realization of right as about certain, strictly caused process of implementation of legal instructions in behavior of people. Quite typical the definition according to which it acts as "such behavior of subjects of law in which practical activities of people on implementation of right and performance of legal duties are embodied instructions of precepts of law (lawful behavior). In other words, realization of right is considered as an embodiment in acts of people of those requirements which in general form are expressed in norms of law as concrete manifestation of process of legal regulation" [9, page 282]. This is the fullest and resisted definition of realization of right.

In other cases realization of right is considered not only as process or external manifestation of process of legal regulation, but also as its final result. In this aspect realization of right is defined as achievement of full compliance between requirements of norms to make certain acts or to refrain from their commission and the sum of actually followed actions.

In theories of legal thought, the fullest answer to this question, it is traced in statements of L.A. Morozova who pays attention to the following features which isolate general regularities inherent in that and other legal category:

- realization is always connected with lawful behavior. Only lawful behavior of participants of public relations realizes rule of law, illegal actions break it;

- first of all, that subject who has subjective rights is interested in realization of right because as a result of realization can get certain benefits, achieve necessary objectives, satisfy interest, etc.;

- realization is not monotonous, unilinear action of right, it is carried out in various forms as public relations which the right influences, methods of legal regulation aren't identical, legal status of subjects of law isn't identical, types of legal norms are various, etc.

Thus, we agree that, it is necessary to understand process of embodiment of legal instructions in behavior of subjects of law as realization of right. Through the point of view, similar understanding of legal essence of institute of realization of right, importance has to be allocated for a problem of definition of forms of realization of right as they sufficiently reflect legal essence of institute of realization and protection of rights and freedoms of minors.

Commenting legal maintenance of forms of right, it is necessary to explain that observance of norms of law represents such form of realization of right which assumes abstention of the subject from commission of acts forbidden by law. In other words, it is a passive form of behavior of the subject. Can be an example of it legal instructions for minors not to disturb public peace at night, not to violate rights and legitimate interests of people, follow rules in public places, etc.

Execution of norms of law is such form of their realization which demands active behavior of subjects of law on implementation of duties assigned to it.

Use of norms of law represents such form of their realization when participants of legal relationship at discretion exercise rights belonging to them.

Application of norms of law is such form of their realization which is carried out by the state represented by the bodies in relation to concrete cases of life.

Thus, realization of right is understood as such behavior of subjects of law in which instructions of precepts of law (lawful behavior) practical activities of people on implementation of right and performance of legal duties are embodied.

In other words, it "an embodiment in acts of people of those requirements which in general form are expressed in norms of law. Realization of norms of law is direct result of legal regulation, its concrete manifestation".

In the context of juvenile relations, in our opinion, will be correct to draw a conclusion that realization of rights and freedoms of minors is understood as a way of achievement of purposes of potential carriers of subjective rights regulated by the

law, an embodiment in acts of subjects of juvenile legal relationship of those requirements which in general form are expressed in norm of law in force.

References:

1. Ormahanov H. Protection of rights of minors in the context of international legal norms // Lawyer. - 2009.- № 4.- 96p.
2. Muromtsev S.A. Definition and basic separation of law. - SPb., 2004. - 328p.
3. Suleimenova S.J. theoretical problems of a mechanism for implementing of water law of the Republic of Kazakhstan // abstract d.l.s. - Almaty, 2009. - 39p.
4. Voplenko N.N. Right in the system of social norms. - Volgograd, 2003 - 217p.
5. Lyubashnits V.Y. Theory of State and Law: Textbook / V.Y. Lyubashnits, Y.M. Mordovtsev, A.Y. Mamychev. - Ed. 2nd ext. and rev. - Rostov n / D .: PHOENIX, 2010. - 700p.
6. Yavich L.S. General Theory of Law. - L., 1971. - 382p.
7. Marchenko M.N. Theory of State and Law: Textbook. - 2nd ed., Ext. and rev. - M .: Prospect, 2009. - 640p.
8. Chistyakov N.M. Theory of State and Law: Textbook / N.M. Chistyakov. - M .: KNORUS, 2010. - 288p.
9. Matuzov N.I., Malko A.V. Theory of State and Law: Lectures. - M., 1997. - 628p.
10. The theory of state and law / Ed. Korelsky V.M. and V.D. Perevalov. - M., 2002. - p. 392.
11. Bekir Kazakhstan launched another program to protect the rights of minors. [Electronic resource] / Access mode - <http://www.zakon.kz/4471308-v-kazakhstane-startovala-eshhe-odna.html>
12. Sadybekov on juvenile justice in the Republic of Kazakhstan // Legal Newspaper. - 2011. - № 3